

ADVERSE EFFECT OF NEUROTOXICITY FROM CAR-T CELL THERAPY: EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT PROTOCOL

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Introduction: Immunotherapy with CAR-T cells is an innovative technique with the potential to remit the aggravating condition of some types of cancer, providing a rapid reduction in the tumor rate and lasting immunity, but this therapy faces an aggravating challenge that has fatal potential, the adverse effect of neurotoxicity. **Objective:** To discuss the mechanisms underlying the neurotoxicity associated with CAR-T cell therapy and to establish prevention and treatment strategies for this potential problem. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Seven scientific articles published in the journals Nature, The Lancet and Biomedcentral (BMC) were used. **Results (Concluded):** CAR-T cell therapy can generate an aggravating condition of neurotoxicity, it is a state of toxic encephalopathy with a broad spectrum of neuropsychiatric symptoms, this condition has been designated as "Immune Cell-Associated Neurotoxicity Syndrome (ICANS)" by the American Society for Transplantation and Cellular Therapy (ASTCT); Cytokine Release Syndrome (CRS) can also occur, where the active components of immune effector cells cause a cascade of cytokines to be activated at a systemic level. This adverse effect can mimic the symptoms of sepsis, aggravating the therapy and potentially leading to organ failure and subsequent death; The management protocol during these adverse effects aims to: Decrease the systemic inflammatory signal through corticosteroids at the same time as decreasing the immune diatribe through suppression, provide the patient with antibacterial prophylaxis through antibiotics, strict monitoring of the patient's vital signs and in more extreme cases, being transferred to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). **Final considerations:** Although the acute symptoms of ICANS and CRS tend to be reversible with support associated with steroid drugs, immunosuppressants and antibiotics, they can be associated with substantial morbidity. It is therefore essential to train staff and develop multidisciplinary strategies for the emergency management of patients with the adverse effect of neurotoxicity from CAR-T cell therapy.

Keywords: Emergency. Assistance. Immunotherapy.

Thematic Area: Management of the critically ill patient.